

INNOVATIVE METHODS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract. *This article deals with pedagogical and methodological features of teaching foreign languages. Also discusses the methodology of foreign language teaching, the history of its development as a science, the types of modern methods used in foreign language teaching methods and their use.*

Keywords: *education system, reforms, technology, approach, features, methods, information.*

The use of innovative pedagogical technologies in education is demand and need in all spheres of educational system at present. It gives a kind of stimulus and motivation in the further development of teaching foreign languages. After the Independence of Uzbekistan there have been great positive changes in the social life of the people and also in all branches of society. At present Uzbekistan has established diplomatic, economic and other relations with many countries of the world. That is why the role of foreign languages, especially the English language, as a means of communication in international relations has become essential. Besides, a modern specialist must know not only one but two or more foreign languages. This is the demand for a specialist in European countries, because a modern specialist must be able to use new technologies and foreign experience in his specialty. In order to achieve this, he should know a foreign language.

Modernization of education system in our country is closely linked with the implementation of innovative technologies into the process of teaching and modernizing the content and methods of education. Modern society needs well educated and qualified specialists who are able to creative thinking and feeling responsibility in solving difficult problems. A humanitarian approach in organizing teaching has become priority in the further development of modern school. The main attention here is focused on the personal interests of the pupils and their personal potential. And this demands different approach to the learners of a foreign language taking into consideration their personality, ability, interests. That is why the main problem for the teacher is to choose the correct methods and aids of teaching which are very effective in getting the aim of teaching. In the late years the new informational technologies are being widely used in the teaching process at schools too. It is not only the use of new technical aids but also the use of new forms, methods of teaching and the new approach in the organization of the teaching process. The main aim in teaching foreign languages at present is to form and develop communicative culture of the pupils, and the habits and skills of using the target language in the process of communication. Now a few words about the aims of teaching foreign languages in colleges and high schools (institutes and universities), because they are the main branches in training specialists. Here it is important to stress out two of main points in training specialists: – their professional training; – their pedagogical training; Professional training requires from the specialists to be master of their job and have profound knowledge on his specialty.

Pedagogical training means to be able to use innovative methods and foreign experience in one's activity of chosen profession. At present one can notice different viewpoints on the term

technology. And in the literature we often meet such terms as “technology”, “pedagogical technology”, “technical technology”, “new technology”, “teaching technology”, “didactic technology” and many others. Now we think that it is time to have the classification of the technological approach. The word “technology” is taken from the Latin words, “techno” (which means art, skill, mastership) and “logos” (science). It came to pedagogical science from production i. d from manufacturing. In the pedagogical literature the word “technology” is used in three meanings: 1) as the synonym of “methodology” and deals with the process of teaching. 2) as the complex of methods used in the concrete pedagogical system of methods, means and forms. 3) as the complex and succession of methods and activities aimed to get a planned result in the process of teaching. If we look back to the history of using technological approach it should be stressed that it appeared in the 60th of the 20th century and technology of teaching meant a definite way of organizing teaching, managed and controlled by a teacher avoiding to the well-planned project of a lesson. The word “technology” came to pedagogies from manufacturing where it is used as technical technology and has three main features: 1) well planning before; 2) a strict succession in carrying out operations of producing planned production; 3) guaranteed result of producing planned production. And the technological approach used in education has four features: 1) the well planned project of the teaching process; 2) motivation of the learners for the theme being learned; 3) a strict succession of the activities directed to learn the objective; 4) a guaranteed result in achieving the goal of the lesson. As it is stressed above there exist several terms with the word technology and each has its own characteristic features, content and function. The term “educational technology” is used in abroad and “pedagogical technology” in our country. In order to make it more clear the functions, features and practical use of the terms with the word technology we’d like to present the following types of it. Thanks to informational technologies we can preserve all information and easily, choose one that we need. Technical technology is used in manufacturing and has above mentioned three characteristic features. Innovative educational technologies have two components: – pedagogical technologies; – didactic technologies. Pedagogical technologies deal with upbringing young generation in the spirit of morality and form feelings of love to motherland, to labor, respect to old and young people etc. In pedagogical technologies there should be worked out the projects against narcotics, smoking, gambling and other negative forms. Such projects should give guaranteed results in upbringing young generation.

Didactic technologies deal with organizing teaching process, choosing effective methods and aids of teaching a target theme and succession of learning teaching material with guaranteed results. So, technologic processes of upbringing and teaching serve for achieving guaranteed results. Learning a foreign language is a multifaceted discipline, in the process of which a person experiences complex psychological changes. In particular, there is a process of comparing a native language with a foreign language. Different teaching methods and technologies are used in this process. With the help of modern pedagogical technologies, comparative teaching of a foreign language with the native language gives effective results. Teaching a foreign language requires knowledge of its methodology. Methods and technologies play an important role in learning a foreign language. There are different methods of methodology in the organization of the lesson. The most widely used methods of foreign language teaching are: the method of communicative didactics, the method of organizing intercultural communication and the method of organizing exercises. The three methods are closely related and complementary. Because the science of methodology is related to the science of didactics, the process of learning a foreign language is

based on communicativeness, and the method of communicative didactics emerges. In the process of applying the method of communicative didactics, the teacher's method of forming intercultural communication is also formed. Learning a foreign language helps you to learn the culture of another country. Exercise technology is important for learning a foreign language. Exercise is the best way to master all the knowledge. Exercise has a positive effect not only on foreign language teaching, but also on the acquisition of knowledge in all areas. The effective organization of the lesson, in which the role of pedagogical activity and modern pedagogical technologies is invaluable. It is important to organize the process of learning a foreign language in a communicative.

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